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AN OUTLOOK AND SPECIALIZED OPINION ON AQUATIC FOOD CHAIN

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ABSTRACT

Food chain is the Linkages of organisms within an ecosystem, in which each link feeds on the one before it and is fed on by the one after it. Only the first link in the chain (called herbage) is a producer and all the rest are consumers. Different food chains intertwine with one another and form the intricate networks called food webs. Nature maintains itself through maintaining a quantitative balance between living species via food chain. First of all Food chain and Food web concepts were introduced in a book published in year 1927 by Charles Elton.

KEYWORDS: Food chain, Food web, Nature

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INTRODUCTION

Many species of animals in an ecological community feed on both plants and animals and thus play multiple roles in the chain. Parasites feed on living tissues, generally without killing their hosts, and may themselves be hosts to smaller parasites. In addition, organisms that die without being eaten are consumed by detritivores, some of which serve as prey for other consumers. The complex system of interrelated food chains in an environment is known as a food web. See more at trophic level. A Food chain is a series of organisms depending on next one to feed upon. This chain is generally shown by arrow links from prey to its predator. Basically a food chain starts from a plants that eat no other organisms in the chain and ends at a species that is not eaten by any other species. A food chain begins with a producer, usually a green plant or alga that creates its own food through photosynthesis. In the typical predatory food chain, producers are eaten by primary consumers (herbivores) which are eaten by secondary consumers (carnivores), some of which may in turn be eaten by tertiary consumers (the top carnivore in the chain).

LEVELS OF FOOD CHAIN

Food chains vary in length from three to six or more levels. Food chain - 1 consists of a plant, butterfly, lizard and an eagle consists of four levels. Where a food chain – 2 consists of leaf, a caterpillar, a bird, a snake and finally an eagle consists of five levels.

COMPONENTS OF FOOD CHAIN

Predator in the food chain

A Predator is any organism that hunts another organism, usually for food.

Prey in the food chain

In a food chain, prey is the organism that is eaten up by a bigger animal (example: In example diagram-1 butterfly is a prey that is eaten by lizards).

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Producers in the Food Chain

Producers are the plants that utilize solar energy for photosynthesis and use air, soil for making their food. All food chains must start with a producer.

Consumers in the Food Chain

Consumers are organisms that eat other organisms. All organisms in a food chain, except the producers, are consumers.

FOOD WEB

Different food chains intertwine with one another and form a network of food chains called Food web.

A number of food chains are available all around in air, water, under and on the land. Another example diagram of a food chain can be seen in Simple Food web-2.

The phrase 'food chain' is a way of indicating how energy moves through an ecosystem.

Components of a Food Chain:

- Plants - 'base' of the food chain
- Herbivores - feed on plants; many are adapted to live on a diet high in cellulose
- Omnivores - feed on both plants and animals
- Carnivores - feed on herbivores, omnivores, & other carnivores
 - 1st level carnivore - feeds on herbivores
 - 2nd level carnivore - feeds on 1st level carnivores
- Decomposers
 - the 'final' consumer group
 - use energy available in dead plants and animals
 - transform organic material into inorganic material

Food chains are more often called food webs because no organism lives solely on another.

TYPES OF FOOD CHAINS:

- Grazing food chain - The grazing food chain begins with the photosynthetic fixation of light, carbon dioxide, and water by plants (primary producers) who produce sugars and other organic molecules. Once produced, these compounds can be used to create the various types of plant tissues. Primary consumers or herbivores form the second link in the grazing food chain. They gain their energy by consuming primary producers. Secondary consumers or primary carnivores, the third link in the chain, gain their energy by consuming herbivores. Tertiary consumers or secondary carnivores are animals that receive their organic energy by consuming primary carnivores.
- Detrital food chain - The detritus food chain differs from the grazing food chain in several ways:
 - the organisms making it up are generally smaller (like algae, bacteria, fungi, insects, & centipedes)
 - the functional roles of the different organisms do not fall as neatly into categories like the grazing food chain's trophic levels.
 - detritivores live in environments (like the soil) rich in scattered food particles. As a result, decomposers are less motile than herbivores or carnivores.
 - Decomposers process large amounts of organic matter, converting it back into its inorganic nutrient form.

CONCLUSION

Nature maintains this biological system by making a quantitative balance between all predator and preys. If we start moving from bottom leveled producers to top leveled predator in any food chain, we will find that number of

predators start decreasing for each next level. For example, number of plants at bottom level is very high, number of butterflies at its upper level less than plants, subsequently next leveled lizards are much lesser than butterflies and at top level eagles are comparatively very less in number than lizards.

The variation in number of species at each food chain level is because if number of predators on a level gets higher than its prey level, they will eat up all their prey and after finishing all preys they will also die without food and the survival of their next leveled species will be endangered too.

